

National Education Policy 2020 and Skill Development: An Economic Perspective

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.14857098

Abstract:

The present research paper highlights on the educational curriculum in the National Education Policy 2020, which was created with the aim of moving towards economic Development. New National Education Policy has been implemented in India. Students will be able to acquire many new skills through this policy. Overall, a skill-oriented curriculum has been designed through this. Mainly because of the rapidly changing employment situation and global ecosystem, it will become more important for children not only to learn, but to learn how to learn. Therefore, de-textualized education should focus on how to think logically and solve problems, how to be creative and multidisciplinary, how to innovate, how to adapt and how to absorb new content in new and changing fields. In that sense, skill development should be done. A major objective of economic Development has been expressed through such skill development. A review of the extent to which the purpose of economic Development will be achieved through this skill-oriented course has been taken through the present research paper.

Keywords: NEP2020 and economic Development, NEP2020 and Skill Development, National Education Policy and Skill Oriented Curriculum.

Introduction:

Skill development has been implemented through National Education Policy 2020. In this policy, importance has been given to every component of the education sector. Through the new education policy, special focus has been placed on holistic education. The vision of this National Education Policy, developed from ingrained Indian values, is to create an education system that directly contributes to the sustainable transformation of India into a just and vibrant knowledge society by providing high-quality education to all, thereby making India a global knowledge superpower. The policy envisages that the curriculum and teaching methods of our

educational institutions should inculcate in students a strong respect for fundamental duties and constitutional values, a strong bond with their own country and a conscious awareness of their roles and responsibilities in a changing world. Thus, the objective of nation building through skill development has been focused through this National Education Policy. A review of the extent to which the purpose of economic Development will be achieved through this skill-oriented course has been taken through the present research paper.

Objectives of Research Papers:

In the new education policy, the objective of economic Development

through skill-oriented curriculum has been included. Accordingly, the objectives of the present research paper have been decided. It mainly involves studying the National Education Policy 2020, explaining the skill development in the National Education Policy, explaining the emphasis on economic Development through the skill-oriented curriculum included in the National Education Policy 2020. These objectives include.

Research Methodology:

While studying any topic or subject, it is necessary to do it in a scientifically approach. One of the most important things in research methodology is the collection of data. In the present research paper, the data have been collected through secondary sources. Along with secondary data collection more emphasis is given especially on primary data collection and observation method. The study of emphasis on economic Development through skill-oriented curriculum included in National Education Policy 2020 is explained on the basis of following points.

Economic Development through skill-oriented Curriculum:

The most important factor in economic Development is competent youth. A key objective of the National Education Policy 2020 is to create a competent youth who is in tune with the modern times. In recent times, the world is undergoing rapid changes in terms of knowledge. Due to the rapid development in the fields of science and technology like big data, machine learning, artificial intelligence, unskilled jobs around the world can now be done by machines instead of humans. At the same time, there will be a growing demand for skilled workers, particularly in mathematics,

computer science, and data science, as well as skilled workers with multidisciplinary abilities in the sciences, sociology, and humanities. Due to the effects of climate change, increasing pollution and dwindling natural resources, a different approach will be required to meet the world's energy demand. Increasing outbreaks and epidemics will create a need for collaborative research and development of strategies in the management of infectious diseases. Social problems arising as a result of these epidemics underline the need for multilingual education. As India moves towards becoming a developed country, as well as becoming one of the three largest economies in the world, the demand for humanities and arts will increase. Such skill-oriented curriculum is included in it. Through this skill-oriented course, an all-round perfect youth will be created.

Another important factor in economic Development is employable youth. Another important objective of the National Education Policy 2020 is to increase the self-confidence of the youth by making them employable. As employment conditions and global ecosystems change rapidly in modern times, it will become more important for children not only to learn, but to learn how to learn. Therefore, education should be de-contextualized and focus on how to think logically and solve problems, how to be creative and multidisciplinary, how to innovate, how to adapt and how to absorb new content in new and changing fields. The pedagogy needs to evolve to make education more experiential, inclusive, integrated, inquisitive, research-oriented, flexible and of course enjoyable. To develop all aspects and abilities of learners; And education, to be useful for all-round development and more

satisfying for the learner, it is imperative that the curriculum includes basic arts, crafts, humanities, sports, sports and health, language, literature, culture, and values along with science and mathematics. Education should develop character and make learners ethical, rational, empathetic and kind and at the same time prepare them for gainful and fulfilling employment. Such skill-oriented curriculum is emphasized in this policy. Employable youth will be created through this skill-oriented course. Thus, the focus is on economic Development through skill-oriented curriculum through this National Education Policy.

Another important factor in economic Development is the greater development of every individual in the country. Also, development of their abilities Personality development of every youth thus shaping the personality of every individual and increasing their self-confidence is another important objective of the National Education Policy .2020 Personality development is given special emphasis through this National Education Policy. This policy is going to be implemented in order to provide the necessary aspects for personality development to the children. The educational policy therefore aims to enable these children to participate and excel in sports and education throughout their lives. Thus, universal provision of quality early childhood development, care and education needs to happen as soon as possible and by .2030Provisions have been made in this policy for this purpose. The National Education Policy prioritizes flexible, multifaceted, multilevel, games-based, action-based and curiosity-based learning, including letters, language, numbers, counting, colors, shapes, indoor and outdoor games, puzzles and logical thinking, problems Solving, drawing,

painting and other visual arts, crafts, drama and talking puppets, music and movement are included. It also focuses on the personality development component such as development of social competence, sensitivity, good manners, courtesy, ethics, personal and public hygiene, team work and cooperation. The overall objective of this National Education Policy is to achieve good results in the following areas. The policy emphasizes on skill-oriented curriculum such as physical development, functional skills development, cognitive development, socio-emotional-moral development cultural, artistic development and development of communication and early language, literacy and numeracy. Through this skill-oriented course, every person will be developed more and their abilities will be developed. In this way, the focus is on personality development through this national education policy on economic Development through skill-oriented curriculum.

In India the new National Education Policy 2020 has focused on educational development. For this some new changes have been made in the education sector. Through this policy priority has been given to the interests of students and their personality development. In order to increase the student's activeness in terms of education, it is expected that emphasis should be placed on the use of various methods such as experiential learning, interactive learning, discovery-comprehension, discussion, analysis, clinical thinking, and questioning by children.

Conclusion:

This educational policy will be implemented considering the ultimate goal of personality development of the youth and students of India. Every student has some innate talents; new curriculum has been added with the aim of discovering them. The curriculum is designed to recognize and stimulate the potential of each student. Talents in every student should be given scope and developed. These talents may manifest as various interests, inclinations or abilities. Students who show special interest and ability in a field should be encouraged to study that field beyond the normal school curriculum. Teacher education includes ways to identify and encourage the talents and interests of such students. The vision of this education policy is to inculcate in students a deep pride in being Indian not only in their thoughts but also in their practice, intellect and action, and to develop knowledge, skills, values and dispositions that support a responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and quality of life, so that, they will truly become a global citizen. Thus, the focus is on nation building

through skill-oriented curriculum through this National Education Policy.

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